

Title: Strengthening PHC System Administration in Nigeria: A Foundation to Universal Health Coverage and a Shield to Emerging Infectious diseases and Pandemics

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Abstract

Introduction

The primary healthcare system (PHC) is the foundation and catalyst to the attainment of universal health coverage, UHC. However, in Nigeria, the capacity of the PHC to act as the vehicle for the attainment of universal health coverage is in doubt, given the present appalling situation of PHC facilities. In light of the potentials of PHC, the authors argued for the strengthening of the PHC system in Nigeria as it could facilitate the attainment of universal health coverage and mitigate the overwhelming impacts of infectious disease outbreaks and health emergencies.

Methods

We reviewed the definition of PHC and its scope as prescribed by the Alma Ata Declaration of September 1978. We also briefly examined the PHC Administration in Nigeria and the pillar of health systems, as it applies to PHC in the context of disease outbreaks and emergencies. We highlighted the opportunities within the PHC to increase health system resilience to epidemics, including COVID-19 and proposed recommendations

Results and Discussion

The current state of the PHC system in Nigeria is appalling. It requires a strong political will to address governance and coordination issues through a complete implementation of PHC Under-One-Roof, a robust and sustained funding stream with significant investments in infrastructures- medicine, medical product and technologies, logistics and information management system, adequate and well-trained human resource for health. To be able to achieve a strong and resilient PHC system capable of achieving UHC and mitigating the impact of disease outbreak and other emergencies, the above-mentioned investments must be anchored on strong community participation, strengthened intersectoral collaboration and strong accountability.

Introduction

Primary health care (PHC) services should provide a minimum package of health services to individuals and communities within the Nigerian health system. Nigeria's health system is weak (Semeeh Akinwale Omoleke et al., 2018; Tilley-Gyado et al., 2016), while the PHC is comatose and incapable of serving its pristine functions (Aregbeshola & Khan, 2017). The health system in Nigeria is challenged by weak governance, sub-optimal health financing, infrastructural deficits, inadequate medicine, products, and technologies as well as human resource (health workforce) deficits (Tilley-Gyado et al., 2016). The primary health care system has been neglected in the past 27 years, since the meritorious era of Professor Olikoye Ransome-Kuti, as a Minister for Health, whose leadership injected life into the PHC system by launching the first national comprehensive policy with a focus on PHC (Aregbeshola & Khan, 2017). He ensured the implementation of PHC policy from 1985 to 1992 as per the Alma Ata Declaration of September 1978 (Aregbeshola & Khan, 2017). The then Minister of Health placed a premium on preventive medicine, strong healthcare at the grassroots, ensured exclusive breastfeeding (for the first 4-6 months of life), increased access to free immunisation services. He also ensured the use of oral rehydration salt by nursing mothers and documentation of maternal deaths that were hitherto not in place. Nigeria achieved a feat during his tenure with a national immunisation coverage of more than 80%. Under his watch, the responsibility of the management of PHC services was devolved to the Local Government Area authority and witnessed the establishment of the National Primary Healthcare Development Agency (NPHCDA) in 1992 (Tilley-Gyado et al., 2016). These actions were intended to strengthen PHC service delivery at the grassroots level with policy guidance from the national level to advance the PHC agenda. His indelible leadership was aborted by the Abacha-led military junta that took-over power (command) from General Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida's military government. However, most of these successes recorded were eroded as evidence suggest that only approximately 20% of the 30,000 PHC facilities spread across the countries are functional (Aregbeshola & Khan, 2017; Tilley-Gyado et al., 2016). These could be due to economic downturn following the introduction of Structural Adjustment Programme, growing levels of

corruption, interruption in PHC policy implementation, fragmented PHC governance and coordination, inadequate health financing, deficit in human resource for health and maldistribution of health workers, poor health infrastructures and lack of essential drug supply (ref).

The primary healthcare service should be the foundation and catalyst to the attainment of universal health coverage, UHC (Lahariya, 2019; Medcalf et al., 2015; Tilley-Gyado et al., 2016; WHO, 2019) Universal Health Coverage as defined by the World Health Organisation is the attainment of equal access for all to quality health services with no financial risk to those in need of them (Medcalf et al., 2015). However, in Nigeria, the capacity of the PHC to act as the vehicle for attainment of the goal of universal health coverage is in doubt, given the appalling situation of PHC facilities at present. This is because the PHC system is bedeviled with chronic governance and coordination issues bothering on a fragmented management structure. In light of the potentials of PHC, the authors argued for the strengthening of the PHC system in Nigeria as it has the potential of facilitating the attainment of universal health coverage and, more importantly, provide a cushion or protective shield from the overwhelming impacts of emerging and re-emerging disease outbreaks. If the PHCs were well-equipped and functioning optimally, much of the burden in terms of clinical management for asymptomatic, mild to moderate cases of infectious disease, for example, COVID-19, could be managed at this level. This capacity at the PHC level minimises strain on the secondary and tertiary healthcare systems. Disease surveillance and contact tracing for COVID-19 and other epidemics could be done at the PHC level with adequate staffing, training and provision of required logistics. To achieve the aim of the treatise, we explored the definition of PHC and its scope as prescribed by the Alma Ata Declaration of September 1978 in present-day Kazakhstan. We also briefly examined the PHC Administration in Nigeria, the pillar of health systems as it applies to the primary health care, and we proposed by highlighting the opportunities within the PHC to increase health system resilience health to epidemics, including COVID-19. Finally, we proposed way forwards and summarised the chapter with a conclusion subsection.

Concept and Scope of Primary Health Care

Definition of Primary Health Care

The Alma Ata Conference of 1978 projected primary health care to the deserved prominence as it put health equity at the front burner of the international political agenda, thus making PHC the nucleus of the World Health Organisation's goal of health for all (Alma-Ata Declaration, 1978). The Alma Ata Declaration defined "primary health care as the essential health care service based on practical and scientifically sound and socially acceptable methods and technology made universally acceptable to individuals and families in the communities through their full participation and at a cost the community and the country can afford at every stage of their development in the spirit of self-reliance and self-determination"(Alma-Ata Declaration, 1978). It is designed as an integral part of the national health system, and potentially a cornerstone of the community's overall social and economic development. The primary health care, if functional, brings health care services closer to where people live and work and is the first contact to the health care system within a continuum of health care services. The world bank, WHO and other partners jointly reported that 90% of the people's health care needs can be met at the primary health level in developing countries (Dohetry & Govender, 2004). This is predicated on the assumption of a functional and responsive PHC system equipped to deliver quality health services.

Primary health care reflects the economic conditions and sociocultural and political characteristics of the country and its communities and is based on the application of relevant results of social, biomedical and health services research and public health experience (Alma-Ata Declaration, 1978). These features have implications on the administration and management of primary healthcare services in Nigeria, as we shall see in this chapter. The Alma Ata declaration's overall goal is for the whole world communities, international organisations and national governments to achieve a level of health that permits populations to lead a socially and economically productive life by the year 2000, and beyond (Alma-Ata Declaration, 1978). Sadly, this was not achieved.

The Millennium Development Goals set for the year 2015 were a useful metric of the performance of PHC, particularly in developing countries, and it clearly showed that a lot more needs to be done in strengthening PHC services if the hope of achieving the newly set target of 2030 for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) would be realised.

Scope of Primary Health Care

Conceptually, the PHC addresses the community's leading health problems through the provision of preventive, promotive, curative and rehabilitation services. Indeed, a functioning PHC system provides services on health education (programmatically termed Advocacy Communication and Social Mobilisation); promotion of food supply and proper nutrition; ensuring an adequate supply of potable water and basic sanitation (now called Water, Sanitation and Hygiene- WASH), maternal and child health care including family planning and immunisation against major vaccine-preventable diseases; prevention and control of locally endemic diseases and epidemics (disease surveillance and outbreak response), appropriate treatment of common diseases and injuries and provision of essential drugs(Alma-Ata Declaration, 1978).

PHC employs a multi-sectoral and multi-stakeholders' approach to the delivery of its mandate. Therefore, it is interconnected with all aspects of community and national development. In other words, it is intimately connected with agriculture and animal husbandry, food supply chain, education, housing, communication and transport, and in some way, the justice system. For PHC to achieve its mandate, all the aforementioned-related sectors must work together in a coordinated and systematic fashion. At the centre of all these is the requirement of the fullest level of community participation and ownership.

The PHC system should be fully integrated into the national health system, and it should operate referral services seamlessly with other tiers of the health service delivery system (secondary and tertiary health care system). It requires a complement of the health workforce, such as the medical doctors, nurses and midwives, community health workers and auxiliaries, and where necessary, the

traditional health practitioners, appropriately trained socially and technically to operate as a team and effectively respond to the health needs of the people at the community level.

Administration of PHC services in Nigeria

Nigeria has a huge population of over 200 million based on projected census population and a landmass of 924,000 Km². It has 36 states and Federal Capital Territory (FCT) with 774 Local Government Areas and 9550 political wards. The country operates a presidential system of government with political and administrative functions devolved to the States. Similarly, the tiers of the health system are supported by the three tiers of the government. In other words, the provision of the Local Government Area administration is to primary health care services; the State Government is responsible for secondary health care services while the Federal Government provides support to the tertiary level of healthcare. At the time of Nigeria's independence from the British Colonial Master in 1960, the health system's focus was curative, and little or nothing was done regarding health system development.

According to the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, the government is committed to providing quality and accessible health services through the provision of primary health care in rural areas as well as the provision of preventive and curative services. Despite the constitutional provision, adequate attention has not been paid to the health sector, including primary health care services. Despite the constitutional provision of other international or regional commitments such as the Abuja declaration, the health sector is yet to enjoy a robust funding vis-à-vis annual budgetary allocation, which has been consistently less than 10% in the last 30years.

The local government authorities manage the PHC services with some support from the state governments under the policy and strategic guidance of the federal government through the National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA). Similar institutions have been created in the State, i.e., the State Primary Health Care Development Agency (SPHCDA), to oversee the management of primary health services at the State level. The SPHCDA has been mostly ineffective as the

management of PHC staff (recruitment, promotion, sanction, re-assignment and training) is domiciled in many cases in the Ministry of Local Government Affairs and Local Government Civil Service Commission, depending on the State peculiarities. This varied, and often fragmented governance and coordination gaps led to the formulation of PHC-Under-One-Roof policy in 2011 to address the issues- specifically PHC management fragmentation, ensure integration of PHC service under one authority and human resource management challenge. The implementation has been relatively slow and varied across States due to bureaucratic bottlenecks and inadequate political will. However, it is very early to assess or comment on the impact of the new policy on the functionality of PHCs and its effect on health outcomes. Due to the weakness in providing basic medical care at the PHC level, there is a huge burden on the secondary and tertiary healthcare system and associated inefficiencies.

Pillars of Health System Strengthening as it applies PHC

While the historical origins of primary health care traverse over a century, starting in heterodoxy from the UK's Dawson's Report, the Soviet's Polyclinics and China's Barefoot Doctors, it eventually received global acclaim with the Alma-Ata declaration in 1979 and is now a core platform within SDG's vision for health and Universal Health Coverage (Frenk, 2009).

Historically in Nigeria, the 1976 Basic Health Services Scheme (BHSS) by the Federal Government was developed as part of the 1975 – 1980 Development Plan (Lambo, 1982). In 1986 the Model PHC concept was introduced and, over time, culminated in the establishment of the National Primary Health Care Development Agency (NPHCDA). This centralizing mandate had always been complicated within the three-tiered framework of executive governance in Nigeria (Tilley-Gyado et al., 2016). Thus in 2015, the Ward Health System, through the framework of the "One functional PHC Per Ward" concept was established and currently focuses on the coordination of PHC revitalization in Nigeria.

All through these moments, primary health care has been championed by various voices as an efficient means of strengthening the health system (Bitton et al., 2017). As long as health system

strengthening is defined as “improving [the] six health system building blocks and managing their interactions in ways that achieve more equitable and sustained improvements across health services and health outcomes,” the interlinkages between health system strengthening pillars and primary health care are apparent (Chee, G., Pielemeier, N., Lion, A., & Connor, C. (2013). We have used the Modified WHO Health Systems Building Blocks model to characterize these pillars. Table 1 below provides a synopsis of the pillars of health system strengthening as they apply to PHC.

Table 1: Health System Strengthening as it applies to PHC

HSS Pillars	Definition	Application to PHC
Governance and Coordination	Leadership and governance in building a health system involves ensuring that strategic policy frameworks exist and are combined with effective oversight, coalition-building, regulation, attention to system design and accountability (WHO, 2010).	<p>Coordination of the PHC system has been fragmented, involving different stakeholder institutions. There is a current drive towards Primary Health Care Under One Roof (PHCUOR) at the centralized level and the existence of Ward Health Systems at the sub-district level.</p> <p>The goal of the Ward Health System has been defined as: “... to improve and ensure access to sustainable, quality, acceptable and affordable health services with the full participation of people at the community level and thereby achieve Universal Health Coverage (UHC)”.</p> <p>The apex body for the coordination of PHC functions is the Ward Development Committee (WDC). Its composition is expected to provide a broad representation of the community. The revised edition of the WHS guideline describes the roles and</p>

		<p>responsibilities of the WDC around needs assessment, programme planning, resource generation, implementation, monitoring, and feedback. However, roles around emergency preparedness and response planning are not delineated.</p> <p>Day-to-day management of PHCs falls under the ambit of the Facility Management Committee (FMC), which usually consists of the head of the WDC, facility officer-in-charge, facility unit heads, and the account officer. The FMC is saddled with resource management, programme management, maintenance, and community linkage roles and responsibilities. FMC platform’s role in supporting the incidence management coordination platform and emergency operation coordination is not articulated.</p>
Health Financing	Health financing refers to the “function of a health system concerned with the mobilization, accumulation and allocation of money to	Financing for primary health care comes from a phalange of sources, including federal, state, and local governments (Tilley-Gyado et al., 2016). There are also funds from individual projects. At the community level, there is a provision for resource mobilization through the drug revolving funds (DRF) (Kress, D. H., Su, Y., & Wang, H., 2016). Informal

	<p>cover the health needs of the people, individually and collectively, in the health system... the purpose of health financing is to make funding available, as well as to set the right financial incentives to providers, to ensure that all individuals have access to effective public health and personal health care” (WHO, 2010).</p>	<p>out of pocket payments by households remain an essential source of financing for healthcare services even at PHC levels with perverse consequences for both health system and public health service delivery (Kress, D. H., Su, Y., & Wang, H., 2016). The Basic Health Care Provision Fund (BHCPF) was established under the National Health Account (NHA). The primary sources of funds come from 1% of the consolidated revenue fund (CRF) of the Federal Government, Grants by international donors, and other funding sources. 95% of the funds are for primary healthcare and national health insurance, while 5% is expected to support emergency medical treatments. The scope of emergency medical treatments delinks it from emergency public health systems, unfortunately.</p>
<p>Health Management Information System</p>	<p>The health information system provides the underpinnings for decision-making and has four key functions: (i) data generation, (ii) compilation, (iii) analysis and synthesis, and (iv)</p>	<p>The PHC is typically a significant source of health information data (Meribole et al., 2014). There is a two-way information flow with the collection, collation, analysis, and dissemination of data in its jurisdiction. PHC also aggregates home-based and community-level data. PHC Facility-level data are usually transmitted upwards to the LGA level, while feedback is expected to be provided by the LGA and</p>

	<p>communication and use.</p> <p>The health information system collects data from health and other relevant sectors, analyses the data and ensures their overall quality, relevance and timeliness, and converts the data into information for health-related decision-making (WHO, 2010).</p>	<p>higher levels. A vital part of accountability and learning for health management information is Integrated Supportive Supervision (ISS) for PHC. ISS was introduced to integrate relevant systems into routine supportive supervision so that constant attention is given to improve, quality, coverage, and data management for PHC services.</p> <p>There have been efforts at the digitalization of interface between other HMIS platforms, and currently, there has been piloting the use of SMS platforms for vertical programmes (Routine Immunization and Malaria).</p>
<p>Pharmaceuticals, Vaccines and Other Technologies</p>	<p>According to the WHO framework for health systems, a well-functioning health system ensures equitable access to essential medical products, vaccines and technologies of assured quality, safety, efficacy and cost effectiveness, and their scientifically sound</p>	<p>The health commodities' supply chain for health commodities in Nigeria is fragmented, including immunization supply chain, to a lesser extent (Ottih, C., Cussen, K., & Mustafa, M., 2018).</p> <p>While the country has essential medicine and health commodities' list inspired by the WHO essential medicines' list, there is no centralized framework regarding health commodities availability. The major sources of arrival for health commodities (outside vaccines) have been through government purchases with both Federal/State/Local Government engaged in purchasing and no</p>

	<p>and cost-effective use (WHO, 2010).</p>	<p>centralized repository available to check-in across these government levels. A large private market also exists for drug purchases with middle-market imports and retail purchases made either through funds from drug revolving funds or direct purchases by service providers as an informal mechanism. There also exist several informal drug purchase referral mechanisms between PHC service providers and local patent medicine vendors (Beyeler, N., Liu, J., & Sieverding, M. 2015). This has been an adaptive mechanism to correct for the chronic stock-outs in commodities at the lower levels. Supply chains also exist for vertical donor-funded programmes with parallel supply chains to ensure commodity provision at the last mile (Woodburn, 2013).</p> <p>The picture of the health commodity supply chain for PHC remains complex. This unclear picture leads to significant challenges with the availability and predictability of health commodities at that level.</p>
<p>Human Resource for Health</p>	<p>The health workforce can be defined as all people engaged in actions whose</p>	<p>PHC systems' performance depends mainly on the availability and quality of the Human Resources for Health (HRH) workforce. The country currently has a workforce density of 1.9 per 1000, which is less than</p>

primary intent is to enhance Health (WHO, 2010).

the 2.28 required for adequate delivery of essential services (Adindu, A., & Asuquo, A. 2013)The NPHCDA began supporting many states in undertaking an HRH Audit for PHC as part of a comprehensive HRH planning process. The current guideline for the ward health system specifies the cadres and numbers required at both the clinical and staff level to ensure a functional ward health system. This is captured in Tables 2 & 3 below:

Table 2: Clinical Staff for Primary Health Care Facilities

	PH Centre	PH Clinic	PH Post
Medical Officer (If available)	1	0	0
Community Health Officers	1	0	0
Nurse/Midwife	4	1	0
Community Health Extension Workers	3	2	0
Pharmacy Technician	1	0	0

Health Records Technician	1	0	0
Medical Laboratory Technician	1	0	0
Junior Community Health Extension Workers	6	1	1

Table 2: Support staff for Primary Health Care Facilities

	PH Centre	PH Clinic	PH Post
Account Clerk	1	0	0
Driver	1	0	0
Health Attendant/Assistant	2	2	0
Security Personnel	2	2	0
Cleaners	2	1	1

In addition to these cadres, the Community Health Influencers and Service Providers' cadre was created to strengthen linkages between community demand for services and PHCs in 2018 (NPHCDA,

		2020). It is expected that there will be a minimum of 10 CHIPS agents in every ward.
Service Delivery	Service provision or delivery is an immediate output of the inputs into the health system, such as the health workforce, procurement and supplies, and financing (WHO, 2010).	<p>The systemization of service delivery for PHC can be tracked from 1994 when Nigeria developed a comprehensive Minimum Health Care Package consisting of 13 components. The service package was revised to a Ward Minimum Health Care Package in 2005 to include Non-Communicable Diseases (NCD) (Okpetu, E. I., Abimbola, S., Koot, J. A. R., & Kane, S., 2018). In 2018 the service delivery packages were expanded to include Emergency and Disaster Preparedness, among other components.</p> <p>The Health Information System has also been expanded to be explicitly linked with Community Surveillance.</p> <p>Ideally, there is a (micro)planning exercise to ensure that the PHCs are providing essential packages of health care that are appropriate, based on the community's need, and scheduled to optimally fit their contexts based on the resources (human and financial) available.</p> <p>The current policy in bridging the link to underserved populations is through outreach services. Communities beyond 2 kilometers from</p>

		<p>the health facilities are expected to be covered through outreach services. Effective outreaches involve participatory planning with community leaders, community mobilization, and delivering services either as single intervention models or an integrated package of interventions.</p>
<p>Community Demand</p>	<p>Communities are groups of families, individuals and other types of networks and social circles that provide support and are often the unit on which health activities are organized and focused (Sacks, E. et al., (2019).</p>	<p>Community participation is a crucial element of both health system strengthening and PHC in Nigeria.</p> <p>The WDC structure has a built-in role for community participation, given that the composition is expected to be made up mainly of members within the community representing different stakes and interests. The updated WDC composition even requires that at least 30% of its members be women.</p> <p>While these are embedded within the guidelines, there is some variability in representation and active engagement across various WDC and Village Development Committee (VDC) platforms.</p>

Opportunities within the PHC system to increase resilience to an epidemic, including COVID-19

A. Coordination

Given the continually evolving dynamics globally and locally, there is an urgent need for adaptive capacity at the level closest to the communities. PHCs, within the ward health system in Nigeria, are well placed to help build epidemic resilience in congruence with International Health Regulations (IHR) (WHO, 2010). Both the FMCs and WDCs are platforms that can easily have expanded mandates towards public health emergency preparedness and response. Public health assessments can be undertaken at the primary health care level, and public health emergency preparedness and response plans, guided by local government and state emergency operation/or any other coordination platforms, can be developed.

Nigeria has a good experience with the incidence management platform under the National Polio Emergency Operation Centre (nEOC) for the polio eradication initiative (PEI). Emergency Operation Centres are government-led initiatives to improve information sharing and joint programming-planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation towards improved public health emergency management (Craig et al., 2017; Shuaib et al., 2017; eHealth Africa). The nEOC was put to good use during the 2014 Ebola Outbreak Response (Craig et al., 2017; Vaz, et al., 2016; eHealth Africa). Nigeria fared better than the other affected West African countries partly because of an already established governance and coordination system (S.A. Omoleke et al., 2016; Shuaib et al., 2017). However, the current polio-based EOC platforms have their incidence management system wholly state-led and state-concentrated (essentially, in States with high-risk for polio) under the guidance, regulation and policy directives of the national EOC. Building and expanding on the current emergency operations centre or coordination platforms (EOC) will involve elements of de-concentration at the local government and PHCs levels with clear road-map for sustainability. At the LGA level, the platform should be multi-sectoral and community-driven. This implies that the coordination platform should be linked with the school management board, water, agriculture and

food-value system, sanitation and hygiene, women and youth groups, security and enforcement agency and traditional leadership. There should be specific considerations for the vulnerable populations, gender mainstreaming during planning and coordination at all levels (PHC-Ward-LGA) within the LGA with oversight and support from the State level.

B. Health Financing

5% of the fund from the national health accounts is dedicated to emergency medical support to be administered by a committee appointed by the National Council of Health (National Health Act, 2014). A review of the emergency medical support policy and structure shows that this skews heavily towards response support at tertiary and secondary care levels. There is an opportunity to expand the fund's scope to include support for public health preparedness and to embed this in a broader framework for emergency preparedness and response.

Current funding for the EOC platform has mainly been donor-based and given the acceptance of Nigeria's documentation for polio certification and the recent attainment of Polio-free certification in Africa (Guglielmi 2020), financial sustainability remains a significant concern. The current COVID-19 context has allowed for increased funding through the World Bank, UN-Basket Fund, and Donor-Partners like GAVI, BMGF that have provided flexible funds to support systems strengthening for COVID-19 and Public Health Emergencies (IMF, 2020). A good proportion of the funds were distributed sub-nationally and are concentrated at the state level. There is an opportunity to take a more robust, systematic, and PHC perspective towards financing for emergency preparedness, and response and exploring PHC platforms is essential. Availability of annual budgets, creation of contingency budget for LGAs and lower levels, clarification, and simplification of access to these funds within the Basic Health Care Provision Fund (BHCPF) and emergency medical support are opportunities for sustainable finances at that level.

C. Health Management Information System

The availability of information to prepare and mount effective public health or medical emergency response is vital. The current HMIS architecture, while it has the required scaffolding to support public health emergency response through the facility and community-based health information system, but this has not been fully systematised (Asangansi et al., 2013) and not fully utilised, especially for disease surveillance and other aspects of primary health care service delivery.

The current WHO-supported integrated disease surveillance and response (IDSR) system exists across Nigeria, and over the years, has been a veritable tool for meeting up to the Acute Flaccid Paralysis (AFP) surveillance indicators through its an in-built performance system to enhance AFP notification (Wassilak et al., 2017; Umeh et al., 2018). Beyond the in-built incentive, the surveillance network expanded in breadth and content. Monthly technical review meetings with surveillance officers from all the LGAs in all the States and Federal Capital Territory in Nigeria were regularly conducted to share data, best practices and map out actions to fill identified gaps from data generated (Omoleke et al., 2018). The surveillance system is both indicators and quality driven. As part of the expansion and strengthening of the information management system, surveillance focal sites were increased and community informants (alternative reporting system) were trained, supported. The community informants were from different trades and backgrounds, which include patent medicine vendors, traditional bonesetters, traditional and spiritual healers, community leaders and traditional birth attendants (Hamisu & Johnson, 2016; Umeh et al., 2015). Nigeria was delisted from the league of polio-endemic countries and Africa was officially certified free of wild poliovirus on the 25th of August 2020. Prior to this date, the polio/AFP surveillance programme recommended an increase in the number of informants from five to ten (10) informants per wards to increase surveillance sensitivity and outbreak detection. Through the GPEI effort, AFP surveillance networks involving both facility-based and community-based informant notification systems were established and were crucial in the polio eradication success in Nigeria (Hamisu & Johnson, 2016;

Umeh et al., 2015; Wassilak et al., 2017). However, this process was vertical as its success was almost exclusive for Polio with surveillance for other diseases lagging (Wassilak, et al., 2017).

The need to fully link surveillance and routine programme information management is essential to ensure data-informed programme planning and PHC service delivery. A well-integrated performance-based incentive to report on diseases using community and facility-based informant systems that have shown great success for polio can be explored and applied to other diseases and local epidemics. Ward Health reconciliation meetings, involving the traditional and community leaders, for routine programme data can be used as platforms for surveillance data reporting and deliberation. The use of technology for some routine programmes in immunisation and surveillance such as e-Surve, Routine Immunisation-Short Messaging Service (RI-SMS), Auto-Visual AFP Detection and Reporting (AVADAR) and Surveillance, Outbreak Response Management and Analysis System (SORMAS), should gradually be scaled-up and expanded to support prioritised interventions. The e-Surve was an innovative system devised by the WHO Nigeria' Surveillance and Data Management System to provide real-time data for active case search conducted by surveillance officers at the LGA level. This tool is equipped with a geo-positioning system and time stamp that could authenticate the surveillance in addition to the paper reporting system. The RI-SMS project was initiated to provide real-time information about vaccination sessions and the number of children immunized by vaccine type (antigen) from each RI-conducting health facility in Nigeria. It provides instant information on the functionality of RI service at a health facility and could prompt immediate action from the local and higher-level management systems. The initiative is not without its attendant challenge (s), as reporting remains sub-optimal since its introduction. AVADAR is an SMS-based smart phone application that enhances the capacity of multiple health workers (beyond the surveillance focal site) and community informants to detect and report AFP case, thus improving surveillance sensitivity (Shuaib et al., 2018). Since its introduction, it has been limited to states where there are surveillance gaps, this may be due to funding for competing needs. However, it complements existing strategies of improving AFP case detection, particularly in security-

compromised areas, hard-to-reach areas and silent LGAs. On the flipside, it is capital intensive at inception but may be cost-effective in the long-term, as there is a need for each informant and health worker or local surveillance officer to have or be given an android phone with sufficient airtime to transmit report (notification). This project is being supported by the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation in collaboration with WHO and Novel-T- a Swiss-based software company (Shuaib et al., 2018). The SORMAS is a German-government supported mobile and electronic-health intervention that enables surveillance officers and epidemiologists to detect diseases based on real-time health facility data and automatic notification (SORMAS 2020). For this electronic disease surveillance and outbreak management system to be scaled-up and successfully implemented, it needs to be supported by infrastructure (electricity and good internet service), adequately-trained personnel and a strong community-linkage via the alternative reporting system. Many electronic tools are currently in use but are mainly vertical in their target and for supervisory purposes. Partners heavily drive the operationalisation of most of the above-mentioned electronic tools. For the surveillance system, SORMAS may provide a solution, however, it is yet to be upscaled nationally for management for all diseases data within the Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response framework. Despite this optimism of scalability, sustainability in financing the operational cost remains a significant threat to its long-term use and effectiveness.

D. Pharmaceuticals, Vaccines and Other Technologies

The logistics management coordination unit (LMCU) concept that was introduced to coordinate health commodities supply chain processes at the national and sub-national level provides an opportunity to incorporate the WHO recommended Interagency Emergency Kit, IEK (Bartels et al., 2016). The IEK contains essential medicines and medical devices for PHC workers with limited training and could complement the essential medicines list for PHCs. It is vital to emergency preparedness and response needs while reviewing the inventory list of stocked medicines and equipment, including Personal Protective Equipment (PPEs). Accessibility of supplies via pre-

positioning and development of needs appropriate distribution plans are essential elements towards ensuring resilience at the PHC level.

E. Human Resource for Health

Given that emergency/disaster preparedness and response are programme components within the updated Ward Minimum Package of Health Care (WMPHC), improving the capacities of the health workforce cadre is an essential required competency. Including disaster management, including preparedness and response in the pre-service training curriculum is an essential list in the curriculum. In-service formal and on-the-job training, including expanding capabilities at the PHC level for remote learning by leveraging webinars where possible, is vital as current and future possibilities for building epidemic preparedness and response resilience.

Within the ward health system, a pool of trained, surge-ready mobile community workforce can be created. This will include creating a database of trained HRH capacity, including geographic mapping of the PHC workforce. The PHC job aids and SOPs on infection prevention control and waste management at the community and PHC level. Though yet to take-off, the available human resources for the health workforce, including CHIPS agents, provides broader opportunities to help with community-based disease notification, surveillance, contact-tracing, and reporting.

F. Risk Communication/Community Engagement & Service Delivery

Framing and designing context-appropriate messaging for disease risk communication is more effective through participatory collaboration leaning on health workers' insights at the primary health care levels to ensure that risk communication for emergency responses conveys the intended message. Risk communication planning and implementation can easily leverage on the available community-level resources (social and traditional communication channels) and more modern platforms to keep the community informed but engaged. Given their proximity to affected populations, it is also possible to institute rumour monitoring and deftly manage misinformation

around disease risk and impact. The traditional, community and religious leaders are very important in advocacy, social mobilisation and risk communication in managing disease outbreak and health emergencies. This is evident in recent successes recorded in polio eradication in Nigeria and Ebola viral disease outbreak in West Africa.

Appropriate emphasis needs to be laid on having a well-trained and well-motivated frontline health workforce. It is thus important to combine training around emergency preparedness with other components such as supervision, group problem-solving, performance management and engaging in prompt community feedback. Higher levels, particularly with state and LGA support, can also aid in planning and implementing simulation and scenario-based training at the PHC level.

Recommendations

A few important steps that need to be taken include:

- Expanding the Emergency Operations Centre Platform beyond Polio towards public health emergencies and ensuring the EOC model is scaled beyond State to the Ward and PHC level.
- Transformation of the EOC platform would also mean a shift from episodic – reactive disease response – towards continuous public health strengthening functions, which involves preparedness planning, capacity building, emergency supply management, and simulations.
- Strengthen financing PHC through the 48% funding for BHCPF, which can be expanded to cater to the Public Health System in synergy the 5% funding Emergency Medical System. Also, re-imagining performance incentives for public health early warning and response to rewards validated disease notification and response at the PHC level with linked impact indicators on the reduction of the burden of diseases at these lower levels can be a useful means of ensuring both data and programmatic improvement of PHC and Public Health services.

- Leveraging on appropriate and modern technologies to expand health spaces at the community level beyond PHCs to schools, recreational areas and homes. This is achievable through adapting mhealth technologies (SMS reminders, hotlines, etc).

Conclusions

Currently, Nigeria's health system is weak, and the PHC system is comatose following decades of neglect by successive national, State, and local government administrations. The author opined that an effective, functional, and resilient primary health care system could potentially act as a shield and provide resilience to the health system in the event of a local epidemic or a global pandemic. Beyond the capacity to provide a shock to massive outbreaks, the primary health care system provides the foundation for a robust national health system and a vehicle to the attainment of universal health coverage.

The status of the primary health care system is indeed a reflection of the overall health and well-being of the people as well as related social and economic indices. Today, the socio-economic and overall societal impact of disease outbreak and ill-health have been ingrained in our memory and for the generation yet to come as a result of the devastating impact SARS-CoV-2 outbreak (COVID-19 disease) all over the world. Consequently, it is a case of social justice and human rights to strengthening primary healthcare services to mitigate future outbreaks, ensure access to universal health coverage and contribute to achieving of health-related SDGs. Therefore, the authors called for a strong and sincere political commitment to the revitalisation of the primary health care system in Nigeria. The authors are aware of the increasing fiscal space for health financing, especially at the primary health care level, however, the process of achieving this potential funding streams is slow and will require a robust monitoring and accountability framework that will safeguard efficient and effective use of financial and human resources.

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